

COVID-19

Unique SARS-CoV-2 genomes found in Antarctic samples raises questions about SARS-CoV-2 origin, lineages

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[Unique SARS-CoV-2 variant found in public sequence data of Antarctic soil samples collected in 2018-2019 | Research Square](#)
[Host genomes for the unique SARS-CoV-2 variant leaked into Antarctic soil metagenomic sequencing data | Research Square](#)

Just as [more](#) and [more](#) evidence of pre-pandemic SARS-CoV-2 circulation before the Huanan market cluster was being found, A group of Hungarian scientists (Csabai et. al.) have recently reported the discovery of SARS-CoV-2 sequences within a set of antarctic soil samples taken in a 3-week-period after 24-12-2018, submitted by the **University of Science and Technology of China** under the BioProject accession [PRJNA692319](#). This BioProject and the relevant short-read sequencing data have been made invisible from direct search on NCBI, but the individual runs themselves are still accessible by typing in the individual Sequence Run ID number SRR13441704, SRR13441705 and SRR13441708 into the search bar in the [NCBI SRA run browser](#). According to the author of PRJNA692319, the DNA from these samples were extracted in December 2019 and sent to Sangon Biotech, Shanghai, China for sequencing.

Table 1. Sample properties. The first 6 columns show basic metadata of the samples. See³ for more information. The 2 extra last columns show the count of reads that align to SARS-CoV-2 genome from the raw R1 and R2 reads. Low complexity reads aligned to the poly-A tail were not counted.

Run	Library Name	Collection date	Isolation source	lat lon	R1	R2
SRR13441700	AKGI_BS1_2018_12_24	2018-12-24	Antarctic soil	62.13 S 58.95 W	112	65
SRR13441701	AKGI_PL3_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.93 W	0	0
SRR13441702	AKGI_PL2_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.93 W	0	0
SRR13441703	AKGI_PL1_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.93 W	0	0
SRR13441704	AKGI_PS3_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.92 W	387	4485
SRR13441705	AKGI_PS2_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.92 W	242	3800
SRR13441706	AKGI_PS1_2019_01_13	2019-01-13	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 58.92 W	0	0
SRR13441707	AKGI_SS3_2019_01_05	2019-01-05	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 59.01 W	0	0
SRR13441708	AKGI_BS3_2018_12_24	2018-12-24	Antarctic soil	62.13 S 58.95 W	349	3537
SRR13441709	AKGI_BS2_2018_12_24	2018-12-24	Antarctic soil	62.13 S 58.95 W	112	161
SRR13441710	AKGI_SS2_2019_01_05	2019-01-05	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 59.01 W	113	106
SRR13441711	AKGI_SS1_2019_01_05	2019-01-05	Antarctic soil	62.21 S 59.01 W	0	0

6 out of the 12 sequencing runs were found to contain sequences that were aligned to the SARS-CoV-2 genome, with more reads aligning to R2 than to R1.

Table 2. Mutations and deletions found in the samples, extracted from the VCF files. The last 3 columns show multiple allele frequencies (AF) and sequencing depth (DP) values, respectively, where the mutation occurred in multiple samples. The leading "SRR134417" was stripped from the RUN ID in the last column.

POS	REF	ALT	Annotation	Gene	AA change	AF	DP	RUN
8782	C	T	synonymous_variant	ORF1ab	Ser2839Ser	[0.66]	[9]	[08]
13694	C	T	missense_variant	ORF1ab	Thr4482Ile	[0.38, 0.29, 0.22]	[47, 34, 35]	[04, 05, 08]
16156	A	G	missense_variant	ORF1ab	Met5303Val	[0.36, 0.54, 0.5]	[25, 11, 10]	[04, 05, 08]
17039	A	G	missense_variant	ORF1ab	Asn5597Ser	[0.53]	[13]	[05]
17634	C	G	missense_variant	ORF1ab	Asp5795Glu	[0.25]	[20]	[08]
18060	C	T	synonymous_variant	ORF1ab	Leu5937Leu	[0.37, 0.38, 0.46]	[27, 26, 26]	[04, 05, 08]
18082	A	G	missense_variant	ORF1ab	Ile5945Val	[0.46]	[28]	[04]
21761	G	del27	disrupt.inframe.del	S	Ile68_Thr76del	[0.37, 0.33, 1.0]	[8, 9, 5]	[04, 05, 08]
23525	C	T	missense_variant	S	His655Tyr	[0.69, 0.61, 0.66]	[13, 13, 6]	[04, 05, 08]
25498	C	T	missense_variant	ORF3a	Pro36Ser	[0.45]	[11]	[05]
26458	G	T	missense_variant	E	Asp72Tyr	[0.5]	[14]	[05]
26895	C	T	missense_variant	M	His125Tyr	[0.51]	[60]	[05]
28144	T	C	missense_variant	ORF8	Leu84Ser	[0.64, 0.71, 0.66]	[17, 14, 15]	[04, 05, 08]
29449	G	T	synonymous_variant	N	Val392Val	[0.43, 0.24]	[32, 29]	[04, 08]

Table 3. Pileup for the mutation positions which were not identified in all samples. The lower and upper case letters denote mutated nucleotides, while dot and comma the original reference nucleotide. (The meanings of other symbols are not relevant, they can be found in samtools' documentation.) We can observe that although mutations were not called by the workflow, mutated bases indeed occur with about the same ratio in all samples.

pos	ref	SRR13441704	SRR13441705	SRR13441708
8782	C	t.TTa..T	TT,..	a.tTtTtT.
17039	A	.\$...G...g..g,	Gg,Gg,,,GTgg^],	..,C.GG,,,,g,
17634	CG..Gg,,,g,,,g,,,,G.....	,G,,,,,,G..	.g.,g,G.GG,,,,,
18082	A	g,,g,,G,GGg.g,,,g,,,g,gGgG	G,,,,n,,,,GG,G,,g,,G*...	.g,gg,,,g,g,g,G,,,,,c.,
25498	C	..gT.TT,t,,,T.^].	T.Tg,..T.tT	..t,t.

Upon further analysis of these genomes, it was found that these SARS-CoV-2 reads contained SNV locations belonging to an extremely early clade located within the A lineage of SARS-CoV-2, while nucleotide positions defining the known early SARS-CoV-2 lineages [v\(8782T, 18060T, 28144C\)](#), A(8782T, 18060C, 28144C) and B(8782C, 18060C, 28144T) are found within these datasets at comparable frequency with each other.

Specifically (rounding to the closest percent), SRR13441704 contained 57% 8782T, 37% 18060T and 64% 28144C, SRR13441705 contained 33% 8782T, 38% 18060T and 71% 28144C, SRR13441708 contained 75% 8782T, 46% 18060T and 66% 28144C.

Multiple other mutations have also been found within these samples, however according to the alignment data from these samples none of the single nucleotide variations (SNVs) found within these samples have reached 100% allele frequency, with both reference and alternative alignment at each position being found at similar frequency with each other across the sequencing datasets.

Figure 1. The smoothed coverage of the human mitochondrial reference genome by the union of R2 reads from samples SRR13441704, SRR13441705 and SRR13441708. The average depth is 85 but there are large fluctuations in the coverage.

Figure 3. The smoothed coverage of the *Chlorocebus sabaeus* mitochondrial reference genome by the union of R2 reads from samples SRR13441704, SRR13441705 and SRR13441708. The average depth is 13.0 but there is a significantly higher coverage for the first ~ 3200nt of the genome. The vertical red line shows the end of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene's end position.

Figure 4. The smoothed coverage of the *Cricetulus griseus* mitochondrial reference genome by the union of R2 reads from samples SRR13441704, SRR13441705 and SRR13441708. The average depth is 12.8 but the first ~ 2600nt part almost lacks any coverage. The vertical red line shows the end of the 16S ribosomal RNA gene's end position.

Alignment of sequences from SRR13441704, SRR13441705 and SRR13441708 to the Homo Sapiens, Chlorocebus Sabaeus and Cricetulus Griseus mitochondrial genome

As these datasets contained unique SARS-CoV-2 sequences that are located very early on the SARS-CoV-2 Phylogenetic tree, The group of researchers attempted to deduce the host sequence for these SARS-CoV-2 genomes within the dataset by aligning the Mitochondrial sequences within these dataset to all mammalian mitochondrial sequences that are available from the [1000 genome project](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genome/1000/). In stead of animal species that lives within Antarctica or animal species that are associated with the wildlife trade, sequences belonging to common laboratory cell lines used in Virology experiments were found within these datasets such as *Chlorocebus Sabaeus* (VERO E6 cells), *Cricetulus griseus* (CHO cells) and *Homo Sapiens* (Huh7.5 cells) were found to be the main mitochondrial alignments within these datasets, indicating that the SARS-CoV-2 sequences were already inside a cell culture when the samples were sequenced. This is consistent with the presence of an deletion of 27 nucleotides at position 21761 in some but not all of the reads aligning to this position within these datasets, a deletion that is specific to the [Huh-7.5](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32011111/) and the [CaCo-2](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32011111/) cell lines. In addition, the mitochondrial reads from *Chlorocebus Sabaeus* and *Cricetulus griseus* show unusual patterns of read depth, where the *Chlorocebus Sabaeus* reads aligns mainly to the 16S MtrRNA and the *Cricetulus griseus* reads aligns mainly to the other parts of the mitochondrial genome that is not 16S MtrRNA. The authors hypothesizes that this may have been the result of Heterokaryons between VERO E6 and CHO cells, induced by virus-mediated cell-to-cell fusion, and would have required both cell lines and the SARS-CoV-2 virus to be located within the same culture.

>gnl|SRA|SRR13441708.1.1 V300043327L1C001R0050000175 forward (Biological) ... >gnl|SRA|SRR13441705.1.1 V300043327L1C001R0050000092 forward (Biological) ... >gnl|SRA|SRR13441704.1.1 V300043327L1C001R0050000058 forward (Biological) ...

Identification Tags
Collection Date; Submission Date
Country; Name
Mutations

EPI_ISL_402124 GWHABKL00000001 MN996528
2019-12-30 2020-01-11
China WIV04
AAAAAAAAAAAAA29892-
EPI_ISL_402127 GWHABKK00000001 MN996527
2019-12-30 2020-01-18
China WIV02
ATTAAGGTTTATACCTCCAGGTAACAAACC1- G21316A A24325G TAGGAGAATGACAAA29859-

>gnl|SRA|SRR11092061.1.1 v300043428L4C001R0010000004 forward (Biological)
CCGCGTCGGG AGTGGGTAAT TTGCGCGCTT GCTGCTTCC TTGGATGTGG TAGCGTTTC
TCAGGCTCCC TCTGCGGAAI CGAAACCTGA TTCCCGTCA CCGGTGTTCA CCAATGTTAGG
CACGGCGACT ACCATCGAAA GTTGTATGGG
>gnl|SRA|SRR11092061.1.2 v300043428L4C001R0010000004 reverse (Biological)
ATTCGAAAGT CTGCGCTATC AACTTTCGAT GGTAGTCCG GTGCTACCA TGGTGAACC
GGGTGACGGG GAATCAGGGT TCGATTCCGG AGAGGAGGCC TGAGAAACGG CTACCACATC
CAAGGAAGGC AGCAGGGCGC CAAATACCC

>gnl|SRA|SRR11092062.1.1 v300043428L2C001R0020000002 forward (Biological)
GCTGAAACCA TGCCATGAAC CTGCTGCTAT ACTTAGTACT ATTTTATTCA ATCCITTAATA
ATCTACTCTT AGACTCCATA AGCGATTTCG CTTTTTTATG GGTACACAG TCGAGTGTGA
CAAAAAAGTT GCTGTTGCTA CCACTACAAC
>gnl|SRA|SRR11092062.1.2 v300043428L2C001R0020000002 reverse (Biological)
GTAATTTGA AACATTATG CATACTGTT GGTAAAAAA GATGACCACT TTAATTAATG
GCAGTTTGA GTTGTAGTGG TAGCAACAGC AACTTTTTGG TACTCTGCA CTGTGTAGCC
CATAAAAAAG GCAATAGCTT TATGGAGTCT

Sequence data that support the findings of this study have been deposited in GISAID (https://www.gisaid.org/) with accession numbers EPI_ISL_402124, EPI_ISL_402127- EPI_ISL_402130 and EPI_ISL_402131; GenBank with accession numbers MN996527-MN996532; National Genomics Data Center, Beijing Institute of Genomics, Chinese Academy of Sciences (https://bigd.big.ac.cn/databases?lang=en) with accession numbers SAMC133236-SAMC133240 and SAMC133252.

SRX7730882: RNA-Seq of Homo sapiens: bronchoalveolar lavage fluid
1 ILLUMINA (Illumina HiSeq 3000) run: 34.3M spots, 10.3G bases, 6.4Gb downloads

Design: Total RNA was extracted from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid using the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit (50) following the manufacturers instructions. An RNA library was then constructed using the MGIEasy RNA Library Prep Set (96 RXN) (Cat. No.: 100006384). Paired-end (150 bp) sequencing of the RNA library was performed on the MGISEQ-2000RS platform.

Submitted by: Wuhan Institute of Virology, Chinese Academy of Sciences

Study: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 Raw sequence reads

PRJNA605983 • SRP249613 • All experiments • All runs

Sample: SAMN14082190 • SRS6151293 • All experiments • All runs
Organism: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2

Library:
Name: WIV05
Instrument: Illumina HiSeq 3000
Strategy: RNA-Seq
Source: METAGENOMIC
Selection: RANDOM
Layout: PAIRED

Runs: 1 run, 34.3M spots, 10.3G bases, 6.4Gb
Table with columns: Run, # of Spots, # of Bases, Size, Published

SRX7730881: RNA-Seq of Homo sapiens: bronchoalveolar lavage fluid
1 ILLUMINA (Illumina HiSeq 1000) run: 61.3M spots, 18.4G bases, 11.4Gb downloads

Design: Total RNA was extracted from bronchoalveolar lavage fluid using the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini Kit (50) following the manufacturers instructions. An RNA library was then constructed using the MGIEasy RNA Library Prep Set (96 RXN) (Cat. No.: 100006384). Paired-end (150 bp) sequencing of the RNA library was performed on the MGISEQ-2000RS platform.

Submitted by: Wuhan Institute of Virology, Chinese Academy of Sciences

Study: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 Raw sequence reads

PRJNA605983 • SRP249613 • All experiments • All runs

Sample: SAMN14082197 • SRS6151292 • All experiments • All runs
Organism: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2

Library:
Name: WIV04-2
Instrument: Illumina HiSeq 1000
Strategy: RNA-Seq
Source: METAGENOMIC
Selection: RANDOM
Layout: PAIRED

Runs: 1 run, 61.3M spots, 18.4G bases, 11.4Gb
Table with columns: Run, # of Spots, # of Bases, Size, Published

The Flow Cell ID in the read headers of the Antarctic sample datasets (Top), compared to the flow cell ID in the read headers of the earliest SARS-CoV-2 genome sequenced using the MGISEQ-2000RS platform (from A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin – PMC (nih.gov)) (bottom). Middle left: GISAID submission date and accession numbers of genomes WIV04-WIV07. Bottom right: library name for the 2 selected runs (one without a corresponding MiSeq run (WIV05), one with a corresponding MiSeq run (WIV04-2)). Structure of the MGISEQ-2000RS header is from Runcer-Necromancer: a method to rescue data from an... | F1000Research

Dating these datasets is more challenging. However, as the MGISEQ-2000RS flow cells used in the sequencing process for these datasets are uniquely serialized, manufactured in series and usually used right after being ordered, it is possible to roughly deduce the temporal order of which two MGISEQ-2000RS datasets were sequenced, using the flow cell ID of the run headers—a run with a lower flow ID likely to be sequenced before a run with a higher flow cell ID, with the difference in time of sequencing roughly estimable using the difference in the flow cell ID as this difference usually reflects the number of runs that have happened between the time of sequencing of the two datasets.

The flow cell ID for the MGISEQ-2000RS datasets within PRJNA692319 and PRJNA605983 are V300043327 and V300043428 respectively, with PRJNA692319 being about 101 below PRJNA605983. This indicates that these contaminated antarctic samples are sequenced at roughly 101 sequencing runs or orders from BGI before the first Huanan market-associated SARS-CoV-2 patient samples were sequenced on an MGISEQ-2000RS platform by the Wuhan Institute of Virology sometime between 10-01-2020 (the sampling date for the “second sampling” of the patients in the publication A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin – PMC (nih.gov)) and 18-01-2020 (the submission date of WIV05, the only sequence within this publication that was sequenced only using MGISEQ-2000RS). This is consistent with the information of the December 2019 date when the DNA from these samples were extracted and sent to Sangon Biotech, Shanghai, China; obtained from the authors of PRJNA692319 by Csabai et al.

If these antarctic datasets were indeed sequenced some times in December 2019, it would be the earliest sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 using the MGISEQ-2000RS platform, and would have been the earliest cultured sample of SARS-CoV-2 that was released intentionally or inadvertently into the public NCBI dataset by date of sequencing. Only 2 other publications involving SARS-CoV-2 may have a date of sequencing close to this period, A Novel Coronavirus from Patients with Pneumonia in China, 2019 – PubMed (nih.gov) PRJNA601736 and A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China – PMC (nih.gov) PRJNA603194, however neither publication used the MGISEQ-2000RS platform for the purpose of sequencing, and neither publication (nor were the publication A pneumonia outbreak associated with a new coronavirus of probable bat origin – PMC (nih.gov)) have performed viral isolation using a cell culture system that involved the CHO cell line. While PRJNA603194 is registered by an institution in Shanghai, the Shanghai Public Health Clinical Center & School of Public Health, Fudan University, Virus isolation was not attempted. Whereas while virus isolation was attempted in primary HAE, Huh-7.5 and VERO E6 cells in the publication associated with PRJNA601736 Neither the publication, the authors of the publication or data from the BioProject itself indicate sequencing being conducted in Shanghai. This indicates that

none of these early publications that involved the isolation and sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 would have lead to the contaminant found within the sequencing datasets within PRJNA692319, and that PRJNA692319 may plausibly represent a cell cultured isolate of SARS-CoV-2 that is already present within a Chinese laboratory before the start of the COVID-19 pandemic.

As all early lineages of SARS-CoV-2 can be found within the same cell culture (s) within PRJNA692319, only a single spillover from this cell culture is required for the formation of all of the early human SARS-CoV-2 lineages.

Tags: [Allele counting](#), [Antarctica](#), [COVID-19](#), [High-throughput sequencing](#), [Metagenomics](#), [NGS](#), [Pre-pandemic circulation](#), [SNP](#), [SNV](#)